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PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Abstract: This article explores the pragmatic features of phraseological units (PUs), focusing on how these multi-word expressions are used in communication to convey nuanced meanings, emotions, and cultural values. It discusses the pragmatic functions of PUs, including their roles in expressing emotion, reinforcing social cohesion, and managing politeness. Additionally, the article examines the implications of cross-cultural differences in the use of PUs, highlighting the importance of pragmatic competence in multilingual communication. Understanding the pragmatic dimensions of PUs enhances both linguistic and cultural competence, facilitating effective communication across diverse contexts.

Keywords: Phraseological Units, pragmatics, idioms, collocations, speech acts, cultural context, implicature, politeness, cross-cultural communication.

Phraseological units (PUs) are integral to everyday language. These fixed or semi-fixed expressions, such as idioms, proverbs, and collocations, carry meaning beyond their literal components. PUs enriches communication by adding nuance, emotion, and cultural depth. From a pragmatic perspective, these units not only convey information but also help shape relationships, manage social interaction, and express attitudes or emotions. The study of their pragmatic features sheds light on how speakers use PUs to achieve specific communicative goals in context. Phraseological units are multi-word expressions that exhibit a degree of fixedness in form and meaning. Unlike free word combinations, the meaning of PUs often cannot be deduced from their individual components. For example, the idiom "kick the bucket" means to die, not literally kicking a bucket. PUs come in various forms, including idioms (fixed expressions), collocations (frequent word pairings), and proverbs (wisdom-based sayings).

Pragmatics and Phraseological Units

Pragmatics focuses on language use in context, how meaning is constructed based on speaker intention, and how listeners interpret that meaning in real-life situations. The pragmatic function of PUs lies in their ability to convey complex meanings efficiently. By using a PU, speakers can encode information about social relationships, cultural norms, or their emotional stance toward a topic. For instance, using the idiom “spill the beans” not only means revealing a secret but also suggests an informal, often light-hearted situation. The choice of a PU in such contexts reflects the speaker’s intention to make the interaction more casual or intimate.

Pragmatic Functions of Phraseological Units

1. Expressing Emotion and Attitude

PUs often carry an emotional undertone that influences how a message is received. For example, idioms like “over the moon” or “down in the dumps” express joy and sadness, respectively. The choice of a PU can convey the speaker’s feelings subtly, without the need for direct emotional language.

2. Reinforcing Social Cohesion

PUs play a role in maintaining social relationships by reflecting shared cultural knowledge. The use of familiar expressions like “a penny for your thoughts” helps establish common ground between speakers, reinforcing a sense of belonging within a cultural or linguistic group. This implicit shared understanding enhances communication efficiency and smoothens social interaction.

3. Managing Politeness and Indirectness

In many languages, PUs serve as pragmatic markers to soften requests, criticisms, or refusals. For example, the phrase “barking up the wrong tree” can indirectly point out a mistake without sounding confrontational. Similarly, the proverb “actions speak louder than words” can offer subtle advice, avoiding direct confrontation while still conveying disapproval.

4. Implicature and Speech Acts

PUs often contribute to implicature, where meaning is implied rather than explicitly stated. When someone says, “let the cat out of the bag,” they imply a breach of secrecy, allowing the listener to infer the underlying message. Pragmatic speech acts, such as making a promise or giving advice, can also be performed through the use of PUs. These units are particularly effective because they condense meaning into recognizable and culturally embedded expressions.

Cross-Cultural Pragmatic Considerations

The pragmatic use of PUs can differ across cultures. While some PUs are universal or nearly identical across languages, others are culturally specific. A phraseological unit that carries a positive connotation in one culture may have a different or even opposite meaning in another. For example, the idiom “to pull someone’s leg” in English means to joke with someone, but a similar phrase might be interpreted differently in other languages.

Understanding these differences is crucial in cross-cultural communication, as misuse or misinterpretation of PUs can lead to misunderstandings or unintended offense. Pragmatic competence, the ability to use and interpret language appropriately in various social contexts, is essential when dealing with PUs in multilingual settings.

In conclusion, phraseological units are rich with pragmatic significance, offering insight into how speakers manage relationships, express emotions, and convey implicit meaning in communication.

Their use is shaped by cultural norms and social expectations, making them a key feature in both everyday conversation and literary discourse. A deeper understanding of the pragmatic features of PUs enhances not only linguistic competence but also cultural sensitivity, helping speakers navigate the complexities of language use in diverse contexts.

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